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ARCHAEOLOGICAL SURVEY ON THE PERSIAN GULF COAST

Archaeological survey has been carried out on the Persian Gulf Coast by myself for six weeks in the spring of 1969, between Jask and Charak, and on the islands of Kish and Hormuz. Survey in the winter 1969-70 was curtailed by illness to two weeks work in the Bushehr Peninsula, near Gavbandi, and near Siraf. Survey covering the Persian Gulf Coast from Jask to Bushehr, and the major islands will hopefully be completed in the winter of 1970.

The two richest areas thus far investigated were the Minab oasis and the Bushehr Peninsula.

In Minab over 36 sites were found with material from Sassanian times onwards. Three sites in the oasis measured close to 1 km. square, near the villages of Saravan, Guru, and Tiab. Two sites in the salt flats to the west of Khargun were exceptional in that over 99% of all glazed pottery collected was of Far Eastern types and testifies to the incredible trading activity of the Minab (Old Hormuz) area in the period up to the 14th century A.D. when the trading centre was removed to the island of Hormuz. Some of the buildings on these sites were constructed of a stone which is not found in the mountains behind Minab, and was probably brought by ship from the Muscat Peninsula. The investigations at Minab are still incomplete.

Eighty-one sites were found on the Bushehr Peninsula, and although many

were very small, three sites of over 1 km. square were found, one at Rishahr and two near the southern end of the peninsula. On all of these the pottery was chiefly Sassanian, with smaller Islamic settlements overlying and also possibly material stretching back to Achaemenid times. Though unfortunately the pottery of this latter period on the Persian Gulf Coast is so little known that as yet no positive identification is possible. Only three small sites, however, were found of the 3rd to 4th centuries Hejira, which confirms the accuracy of the geographical writers of that period who ignore the Bushehr Peninsula entirely.

The largest individual site on the coast is, of course, that of Siraf where the area within the city walls is approximately 2 km. by 800 m., although the exact extent is impossible to judge as the eastern edge of the site is under the modern village of Tahiri. The suburbs cover another square kilometre. For almost 30 km. in each direction there are a large number of contemporary sites, and near Dayer is another city site, Bibi Khatun, over 1 km. square and with surface pottery identical to that at Siraf.

The large ruined site on the North shore of the island of Kish was also over 1 km. square. The pottery on the surface confirms the history of the site as given by the documentary sources. In the 11th century A.D. Kish began to usurp the trade of Siraf, but by early in the 14th century A.D. the military forces of the rival commercial power of Hormuz occupied the city, and turned its international trade away to Hormuz. However there is occupation on the island of Kish at an earlier date, and on the coast opposite a large number

of small sites of very early Islamic date were clearly concerned with pearl fishing.

The site on the Northern end of Hormuz Island was Kish's successor to the trade of the Persian Gulf. The fort which in its present state dates from the Portuguese occupation should almost certainly incorporate an earlier fortification, as excavations at Bahrain have shown that the Portuguese fort there was merely an adaptation of an earlier Islamic fortification. The site is of especial interest since we possess contemporary figures for the population, and drawings which indicate the type of housing. When a study of the surface area involved has been completed it should be possible to provide an estimate of population density which should apply to other coastal sites too.

The most recent major mound site is that at Kung, near Lengeh, where pottery of the 17th century A.D. stretches on either side of the present town.

When my field work is completed, and when the material has been properly prepared, I will send a copy of a detailed final report, with photographs and maps. I hope that in the interim this brief note will give some impression of the research I am doing.

RESEARCH PROJECT

My research project is entitled: "An archaeological investigation of pearling and commerce in the Persian Gulf, 400 B.C. to 1000 A.D.". I intend, using primarily archaeological methods, to study the commercial conditions in the Persian Gulf in the formative period during which the great trading centres of the Early Islamic Period, like Siraf and Old Hormuz, originated and developed. Emphasis will be placed on an investigation of the origin, growth, and commercial role of the pearling industry, which my current research on trade patterns in Southern Iran during Islamic times suggests might have played a central role in the generation of commerce and of capital formation.

The archaeological fieldwork for this project will involve an intensive archaeological survey of the South shore of the lower Persian Gulf with a close investigation of both archaeological sites and oyster middens. It will require the formulation of a regional typology for the period 400 B.C. to 500 A.D. based on already excavated stratified pottery as a supplement to the good typology from Siraf, c. 500 to 1000 A.D..

The lower Persian Gulf was chiefly remarkable in mediaeval Islamic times for the great port cities built on its inhospitable shore, such as Siraf, Kish, and Hormuz. Each in its heyday flourished from the products of a far flung commerce and was considered among the richest cities in the world. In my thesis, the draft of which I intend to complete by December 1971, I discuss the items of trade, the rise and fall in succession of

medieval trading centres, and attempt to discern the mechanisms of commerce. This research has utilized Islamic, Chinese, and European documentary sources, but has fundamentally depended on intensive archaeological survey of the Iranian coast. The results, which I discuss in the Outline of Doctoral Research attached to this project, will, I hope, establish that a large scale and careful examination of surface remains in conjunction with a stratified ceramic typology can prove a valuable historical tool. A major conclusion from this research is that those cities which flourished in the early Islamic Period, 7th to 10th centuries A.D., were larger in area and apparently better built and more prosperous than any of their successors. Furthermore, a large number of other sites have surface material which belongs to the period 400 B.C. to 600 A.D.. It is undoubtedly in this period where one can most profitably examine the fundamental question of why, while the political orientation of the Persian Gulf was directed towards Mesopotamia, the cities of the lower Gulf rather than those of the fertile upper Gulf came to attain commercial dominance.

Both archaeological and historical material combine to indicate that the pearling industry, which is first indisputably referred to in the Persian Gulf in the 4th century B.C., played an important role in the establishment of this dominance. My archaeological survey on the North coast of the Gulf has revealed on barren sections of coast a large number of sites, especially of Sassanian or very early Islamic date. The existence of these sites is alone explicable by the presence of enormous piles of oyster shells. In addition, despite the paucity of information from Islamic sources, Indian, Chinese, and Western writers point out the importance of the trade in

Persian Gulf pearls, praising them as the finest in the world. Hindu belief in the aphrodisiac and healing qualities of dissolved pearls and a widely held view that the pearl par excellence was the prerequisite of royalty maintained the value of pearls. The economic significance of pearls was principally in that they were the only product of the lower Persian Gulf in demand in the Orient, and one of the very few products beside precious metals which the Islamic and Western worlds could supply to finance their purchase of oriental spices and silks. I suggest then that it was the trade in pearls which to a large extent enabled great trading centres to develop in the lower Gulf rather than on the edge of Mesopotamia.

However, the pearling industry, which at least in the last eight hundred years has centred on the Arabian side of the Gulf, cannot be studied solely in terms of indications on the Persian shore, nor should it be studied outside the broader context of Persian Gulf commerce. My research has shown the Persian Gulf to be much more of a waterway than a barrier. Persian coastal sites had many times more contact in terms of trade in pottery, glass, and stone with towns up to five hundred miles away on the coast than with cities one hundred miles inland across the barrier of the Zagros Mountains. On the Persian side, from the archaeological material, migration and trade could only be studied in terms of local trade and movement on the Gulf coast, from inland Iran, and imports from Mesopotamia, the Far East, or Egypt. My preliminary visit to the South side of the Persian Gulf, however, confirms the existence of a very strong contact between the Arabian and Persian shores. It is clear that archaeological survey on the Arabian coast, as well as providing evidence on ancient

pearling, will allow the reconstruction in the lower Persian Gulf of the pattern of settlements and trading contacts within which the industry was carried out.

The area to be investigated archaeologically is the South shore and islands of the Persian Gulf from Ras al Khaimah to Bahrain. All sites investigated will be recorded in terms of location, dimension, character of habitation, and resources, and a quantitative sample of artefacts collected from the surface. For research on the pearling industry, the locations and, as far as possible, the volumes of shell middens will be recorded, and a quantitative sampling made of the different shells present. Miss M.E. Prickett of Harvard University has undertaken to study and publish any material predating the period of this study.

The area, which I have personally visited, promises to be as well suited to research as has been the Persian shore. Present village settlement is small and impoverished, and rarely masks older settlement. The oil towns of the last decade are generally sited with little regard to locational factors which carried weight in the past, and of the towns of the area only three, Manama, Sharja, and Dubai, may mask older settlement. Insecurity has necessitated the frequent abandonment of villages and towns. The uncertainty of water supplies has led to a great deal of migration of settlement, especially in sandy areas. In rocky regions movement has been facilitated since settlement is made possible even in waterless areas where soil conditions permit the use of cisterns to collect storm water run off.

Fundamental to the success of this project is the compilation of a reliable series of stratigraphically dated pottery types to enable the accurate dating of surface collections. For the very late Sassanian Period (c. 5th to 7th centuries A.D.) and Islamic Periods, the current excavations at Siraf, with which I am closely associated, are providing a first rate stratigraphic chronology based on large samples of pottery. My own excavations at Sirjan and Tepe Dasht-i Deh serve to fill in the gaps for early Islamic pottery not represented at Siraf. A sequence from Achaemenid to Sassanian is emerging from the continuing Harvard excavations at Tepe Yahya, with which I am closely in touch. In Bahrain the Danish Expedition has material from so called "Hellenistic" levels on the Qalat Bahrain tell, and in Kuwait, a well dated 4th century B.C. temple complex has been excavated. Material from excavations such as those at Hippur and Selucia in Iraq might prove of relevance, and I have recently obtained from the University of Michigan microfilmed information on the pottery from Selucia. This material, compared and collated, supplemented if necessary by my own sondages, should provide the firm chronological and spatial framework necessary for valid surface study.

It is intended to use the surface data in the manner I have tested in my current research, and which I describe in my Outline of Doctoral Research. The information collected should enable the mapping of the size and distribution of settlement in given ceramic periods. By analogy to the material already collected on Islamic settlement, this will provide data on the mobility of settlement, and the varying demographic and political feci of the Gulf. The distribution of specific pottery types should, as in the

Islamic Period, provide material on the changing trading links of different districts. Extensive information should be obtained on the size and role of the pearling industry at different periods.

The pearling industry has left unique archaeological traces in the area. Pearling in the Gulf is still traditionally carried out in small boats which land their catch of oysters as close to the pearl beds as landing places and water supply permit. The oysters, opened on the shore, lie in middens of varying sizes mixed with pottery and other occupational debris. This pottery permits accurate dating of many oyster middens. Furthermore, analysis is simplified since pearling settlements seem to have continually moved, either with slight changes in the pearl beds, or more likely, with changes in water supply or other factors. The large beds off Bahrain have unfortunately been fished in a different manner. Large boats remain on the beds for weeks, drawing water from submarine springs and opening the oysters on board. Undoubtedly this method of pearling has grown more important with the great developments in boat building in the last five hundred years, though probably pearling in this manner has always been carried on. However, both through the presence of submarine springs and of the distance of the banks from shore, the Bahrain banks are unique, and their example in no way invalidates the archaeological data from other pearling areas.

Although the first indisputable references to pearling are from the 4th century B.C., the industry almost certainly originated earlier, and an attempt will be made to examine its origins. To this end references will be collected on pearls from excavated contexts in the Near East and the West.

Certain scholars (notably G. Bibby) suggest that pearls, if found at all, are extremely rare in 3rd and 2nd millennium B.C. contexts because of simple chemical decomposition. Pearls, however, should be preserved where mother of pearl has been found, since they are chemically identical. Therefore, particular attention will be paid to sites where mother of pearl is preserved. Passages in Sumerian, Akkadian, and Babylonian literature which some scholars have taken as references to pearling will be collected and discussed. Already the opinions of several orientologists have been canvassed on this subject. A heap of oyster and other shells excavated by the Danish Expedition to Bahrain, associated with 3rd millennium B.C. sherds, will be investigated to test whether the remains are those of protohistoric pearling, as G. Bibby suggests, or merely of food debris. For, by analogy to villages today where shell fish is eaten, pearl oyster shells when found in food middens are characteristically mixed with fish bones and other shells. Pearling middens, on the other hand, invariably contain a high proportion of shells of the pearl oyster (Margaritifera vulgaris), although shells of other bivalve molluscs (Lamellibranchia) which can on rare occasions contain pearls are often found.

Within the past month essential practical preliminaries to fieldwork have been carried out in the Trucial States and Bahrain. The Government of Abu Dhabi, a state which has a long coastline opposite many of the richest modern pearl beds, has assured me of its good will towards the project and has invited an application for a contribution towards field and transport expenses for a survey with sondages in Abu Dhabi in the spring of 1972. Dr. Frifelt, the director of the Danish Archaeological Mission in Abu Dhabi,

and officials of the Abu Dhabi Petroleum Company have provided practical advice and guidance. The possibility of survey in the Northern Trucial States has been discussed in Dubai with officials from the Trucial States Development Council and the British Political Agency, all of whom have assured me of their cooperation. In Bahrain I have made arrangements to meet the Minister of Education. If the Governing Body approves this present application, a second trip to Abu Dhabi will be undertaken in the late summer of 1971 to advance negotiations with the Department of Information and Tourism concerning survey in Abu Dhabi. It seems clear at least that even with the changing status of the Persian Gulf Sheikdoms there are no political barriers, but rather every offer of assistance for serious research.